

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Michelle R. Maziwisa and Jaap de Visser

Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape
with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

Partners

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in South Africa is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of

Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of the Western Cape: Michelle R.

Maziwisa, Jaap de Visser

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia

Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra

Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Tobias Fischer/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.2. Intergovernmental Cooperation in Fiscal and Financial Management: Bulk Resources for Municipal Services

Michelle Rufaro Maziwisa, *Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape*
Lungelwa Kaywood, *South African Local Government Association*

Relevance of the Practice

The Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) requires extensive consultation before an organ of state can increase the price of a bulk resource supplied to a municipality or municipal entity. This forms part of government's effort to ensure consistent policy implementation and achievement of macro-economic objectives. This process is comprehensive and must be completed timely and contain motivations to be tabled in Parliament or the relevant provincial legislature. Careful planning is required to meet the obligations of the MFMA before the pricing amendments can take effect.

Local government is generally the major provider of essential services to communities and so their ongoing financial sustainability is important in meeting national objectives. All municipal budgets must be introduced and put forward for debate and approval in council no later than 31 March each year and adopted before 1 July which provides improved certainty in the process. As the purchase of bulk services makes up a significant component of municipal expenditure (roughly 25 per cent) and will impact directly on the tariff policies adopted by council, it is imperative to coordinate and finalise the pricing from bulk resource providers in a timely manner. Municipalities and bulk service providers are encouraged to take into account the government's broad economic objectives and adhere to the inflation targets when concluding their bulk and retail tariffs. Related mainly to report section 2 on local responsibilities, section 3 on local finances, section 5 on intergovernmental relations and section 6 on people's participation, this practice note is relevant for the LoGov-project to the extent that it affects bulk municipal services, municipal budgeting and consultation with communities as well as how other organs of state plan and cooperate with one another on matters of national interest.

Description of the Practice

According to Circular no 23 of the MFMA, the water boards should demonstrate how they have taken into consideration SALGA and National Treasury comments before the proposed tariffs

can be passed. In response to this requirement, SALGA annually undertakes the review of the water boards' proposed tariffs. The 2019/20 review included analysis of documents submitted by water boards consisting of the proposed tariff submission to SALGA and business plans. The MFMA provides two significant features in relation to the provision of electricity, water and other bulk resources to municipalities and municipal entities. Firstly, if an organ of state intends to increase the price of such resources, it must undertake a comprehensive consultation process, which must be completed on or before 15 March in any year. Secondly and to complement the consultation process, National Treasury is required to monitor the pricing structures and payments made by municipalities and municipal entities to organs of state for the supply of bulk resources. To do this, organs of state are required to submit monthly statements to National Treasury setting out payments received, arrears and any action taken to recover arrears from municipalities and municipal entities (Section 41). Table 1 describes the practice regarding the approvals for bulk water service providers' tariffs.

Table 1: Description of the practice- bulk resources for municipal services (Water)¹³⁸

Action	Date
Department of Water Services (DWS) provides resources for 3 consecutive years to water service providers	Prior 15 September
Bulk water service provider calculates tariff	Prior 30 September
Consultation with water services authorities	Oct & November
DWS preliminary review meeting of bulk water service provider's tariffs	November
Bulk water service provider's submission to the National Treasury (NT) & SALGA requesting written comments	Prior 7 December
SALGA and NT to provide comments	Prior 25 January
Formal submission to DWS including comments by SALGA, municipalities & NT	After 25 January
Bulk water service provider's tariffs tabled in Parliament	15 February
Any amendments to tariffs are tabled in Parliament	1 March
Water service providers are notified of tariff increase in writing	15 March
Water services authority tariff determination process:	
Water services authorities to comply with other regulatory processes	After 15 March
Water services authorities to table draft budget before municipal council	Prior 31 March
Implementation by water services authorities	1 July
Water services authorities submit pro-forma statements on water and sanitation tariff determination to DWS as reflected in norms and standards	Immediately after 1 July

¹³⁸ National Treasury, 'Schedule 3: Norms and Standards in Respect of Tariffs for Bulk Water Services Supplied by Bulk Water Services Providers or Regional Bulk Water Utilities to other Water Services Institutions' (Government Gazette No 39411, Republic of South Africa, 13 November 2015) 123.

Assessment of the Practice

From SALGA's perspective, the main objective of the analysis was to assess applications received from water boards for tariff increases for the 2019/20 financial year. SALGA undertook to comment on these applications with a view to protect the interests of the municipalities that are served by water boards. In undertaking this analysis, SALGA took into consideration that bulk water tariff increases are required in order to ensure that water boards remain financially sustainable, but this must be balanced with the need to ensure that water remains affordable to municipalities and, ultimately, the end users. The main historic challenge with regards to SALGA's participation in bulk water IGR processes (specifically, in the tariff increase consultations with local government, by the water boards as regulated through the MFMA) has been the lack of consultation with municipalities which made the submissions and comments weak. The challenge of SALGA to fully represent local governments often resulted in unaffordable tariffs being imposed on local governments, which in turn, passed on the costs to consumers through service charges. From the Treasury perspective, SALGA's involvement in the tariff consultations for bulk water services allows for the monitoring of the pricing structure of the organs of state for the supply of electricity, water or any other bulk resources to municipalities and municipal entities as well as payments made for such bulk resources. Another challenge more broadly is that there seems to be no 'board' as such that is formally responsible for regulating water boards, unlike electricity which has a clear regulator. It is therefore especially important to ensure that submissions by SALGA are taken into account as SALGA is in a way playing a monitoring role although it is also representing local governments in the budget forum.

The practice is one of the useful means to ensure local government budgets are credible to the extent that they are based on realistically anticipated revenues and expenditures. For example, following the review, SALGA rejected eight out of nine tariff submissions from the water boards and urged them to take into consideration the points of reservation SALGA made against their tariff proposals for the 2019/20 financial year. This was premised on the review which revealed that overall, the tariff increases requested by water boards were extremely high and unaffordable to the local government sphere. Largely, the high tariffs were attributable to high input costs, unrealistic demand projections that did not match historical actual consumption of the service etc.¹³⁹ There is differentiation in terms of how the practice works in urban and rural settings in that, rural municipalities pay higher tariffs due to higher costs of service provision (topography is the main cost driver). This further exacerbates the financial constraints affecting most rural municipalities characterised by poor or no revenue base and places an additional burden on the national fiscus.

¹³⁹ This is based on SALGA's own assessment reports which are not published, but are presented to Parliament and water boards as part of the consultation process.

While SALGA made input, the extent to which its recommendations (as the voice of local government) have been taken into consideration reveals a loophole in the IGR system which in turn affects both rural local governments (RLG) and urban local governments (ULG) negatively. The water boards do not always implement the comments / inputs from both SALGA and National Treasury, and consultation is a compliance driven exercise that is often not done in good faith and consultation from SALGA's view.¹⁴⁰

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Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

